

Isolation and identification of helminthes parasites from black partridge *Francolinus francolinus* birds in Al-Diwaniyah province/Iraq

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Abstract

A total of 57 from black partridge *Francolinus francolinus* were collected from different parts in Al-Diwaniyah province /Iraq for the period between August to December 2019 to isolate and identify helminthes parasites. The overall prevalence of recovered helminthes was (63.15%) and recorded four species included two Cestodes were: *Raillietina tetragona* (76.13%) and *Cotugina* sp. (55.26%), two Nematodes were: *Heterakis gallinarum* (63.15%) and *Heterakis isolanche* (44.73%). A significant difference was reported between male (65.62%) and female (60%) of infected birds at ($P \leq 0.05$). Double infection rate was more common (50%) than single infection rate (30.55%) and triple infection rate (19.44%).

Keywords: *Francolinus francolinus*, parasites, helminthes

How to cite this article: Al-Aredhi H.S (2020): Isolation and identification of helminthes parasites from black partridge *Francolinus francolinus* birds in Al-Diwaniyah province, Iraq, *Ann Trop Med & Public Health*; 23(10): SP231013. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.36295/ASRO.2020.231013>

Introduction

There are about 9,000 species of birds in the world, they are hot-blooded animals feed on grains, mice, insects, rodents, fish, fruits, dead animals and smaller birds (Rogers, 2002).

Birds were infected with internal parasites that causing pathological effects, including reduced eggs production, loss of weight and may cause hemorrhage that make them vulnerable to secondary infections with bacteria and fungi (Adejimi and Oke, 2011), In addition, infected birds with helminthes were unable to stand, suffer from lethargy and sometimes mucous diarrhea mixed with blood (Rodriguez *et al.* 1997), and dying in severe infections due to their host participation in food and toxic secretion affecting hormones and enzymes, also contribute to the transmission of infection to field animals, fish farms and domestic animals such as cats, dogs and sometimes humans (Kulkarni *et al.* 2001).

Several studies have reported different species of helminthes parasitic on birds in Al-Diwaniyah province, Al-Jubori (2010), reported infected domestic chickens with nine species of helminths including *Raillietina tetragona*, *R. cesticillus*, *Ascaridia galli* and *Heterakis gallinarum*, Al-Shaibani (2015) found *Meleagris gallopavo* infected with seven species of helminthes were *Raillietina cesticillus*, *Raillietina tetragona*, *Choanotania infundibulum*, *Hymenolepis* sp., *Capillaria* sp., *Heterakis gallinarum*, Al-Aredhi (2019) studied external and internal parasites in resident and migratory aquatic birds in Al-Dalamj marsh and recorded thirty four species of parasites, including: *Raillietina tetragona*, *Cotugnia* sp., *Heterakis gallinarum* and *H. dispar*.

The current study aims to isolate and identify helminthes from black partridge bird and show the relationship of the bird's gender to infection.

Materials and methods

Collecting 57 black partridge *Francolinus francolinus* (32 males and 25 females) from different parts in Al-Diwaniyah province during the period from August to December 2019, birds were transferred to the laboratory of parasites in the department of biology/ college of education/ University of Al-Qadisiyah and identify by Allouse (1960).

Dissected the birds from the chest till end of abdomen, then isolated digestive tract and divided it into parts, helminthes were isolated prepared according to the method described by (GarciaandAsh,1979), Cestodes identify by Schmidt (1986) and Nematodes by (Soulsby *et al.*, 1982), The results were analyzed by using chi-square at (P<0.05) (Al-Rawi, 1984).

Results:

Out of the 57 birds examined, 36 (63.15%) were infected by four species of gastro-intestinal helminths consist of two species of Cestodes were *Raillietina tetragona* (76.13%) and *Cotugina* sp.(55.26%) two species of Nematodes were *Heterakis gallinarum*(63.15%) and *Heterakis isolanche* (44.73%) as table (1) figures 1-4.

Table (1): Parasites species isolated from black partridge birds in Al-Diwaniyah province (N=57)

Helminthes species	No. infected	Percentage	Site of infection
<i>Raillietina tetragona</i>	29	76.13%	Small intestine
<i>Cotugina</i> sp.	21	55.26%	Small intestine
<i>Heterakis gallinarum</i>	24	63.15%	Cecum
<i>Heterakis isolanche</i>	17	44.73%	Cecum

A significant difference was found between male and female of infected birds at ($P \leq 0.05$), as table (2).

Table (2): Infection rate of parasites species according to gender.

gender of birds	No. examined	No. infected	Percentage
Male	32	21	*65.62
Female	25	15	60
Total	57	36	

*indicate a significant difference using Chi square test at ($P < 0.05$).

Double infection rate was more common (50%) than single infection rate (30.55%) and triple infection rate (19.44%) as table (3).

Table (3): Infection type of parasites in examined birds.

Infestation type	No. infested	percentage
Single	11	30.55
Double	18	*50
Triple	7	19.44
Total	36	

*indicate a significant difference using Chi square test at ($P < 0.05$).

Discussion

Black partridge birds species feeds on insects, larvae, beetles, bugs, ants and the sever cold and drought contribute to determining the numbers of their population (Liao *et al.*, 2007).

In current study reported four species of helminthes and this agree with Mohammad (1990) who reported *Raillietina tetragona*, *Cotugina digonopora*, *Heterakis gallinarum* and *Paroncocerca rousseloti* from black partridge in Baghdad area.

The cectodes *Raillietina tetragona* and *Cotugina* sp. infected various types of birds, such as turkeys, pigeons, domestic chicken and aquatic birds and have a simple life cycle that requires only one intermediate host such as ants, beetles and earthworms (Adang, 1999).

Nematode *Heterakis* spp. are the most common parasitic pathogens infect cecum of both wild and aquatic birds and cause Heterakidosis (Amundson *et al.*, 2016).

It is known that the infection with nematode of the *Heterakis* spp. increases in the winter and Autumn especially in young birds (Deeley, 2007), This is also confirmed by Hennache and Ottiviani (2006) who note the high infection rate with nematodes of genus *Heterakis* and *Capillaria* in the autumn especially among young birds until the age of two months, because the nematodes reproduce during this period.

Infected birds with *Heterakis* suffer from diarrhea, weight loss, nodular typhlitis and death in severe infections (Baker, 2007), in addition to co-infection with *H. gallinarum* and *H. isoloncheare* more pathological than single infection (Menezes, 2003).

Although the great similarity between *H. isolonche* and *H. gallinarum*, Halajianet *al.*, (2013) revealed the possibility to distinguish between the two species through the size of spicules, in *H. gallinarum*, spicules are sub equal in length, the right is three times longer than the left but in *H. isolonche* the left 1665–1780 (1723) μm and the right length of 1770–1800 (1785).

Significant differences was observed between male and female birds in infection rate with helminths parasites, this is agree with both of Bui and Haddabi (2005) when recorded a higher infection rate with parasites in male chickens compared to females in Nigeria and Fedynichet *al.* (2005) who noted a higher infection rate with parasites in male geese compared to females, due to males live in different environments and feed on a variety of sources.

In the current study, infection with two species of helminths parasites is highest, this is agree with Frantovo (2000) who explained that birds feeding on different types of food sources, especially insects, which are intermediate hosts for some intestinal helminths.

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